

A STUDY ON WORKPLACE CULTURE AND ITS IMPACT ON LIFESTYLE

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Abstract:

Everyone's life now revolves on change, even those in the corporate world. Despite being required to adapt their routine operations, most workplaces had varying attitudes toward change. The purpose of this study is to determine how workplace culture-related changes in lifestyle impact businesses. Furthermore, examine how to adopt lifestyle changes due to workplace culture. Employers must most importantly show a commitment to health and wellness that is fully linked with their mission, values, and long-term vision, paving the path for long-term lifestyle improvements. Developing friendships with, taking an interest in, and caring for one's co-workers. Helping one another, especially by being compassionate and understanding toward those who are suffering. Averting charges and overlooking mistakes. Inspiring one another in work. Proving the significance of the work. Showing one another thanks, respect, trust, and honesty.

Keywords - Lifestyle Change, Organizational Change, Workplace Culture, Innovation, Resistance to Change

INTRODUCTION

The impact of work-life programs on organizational structures and cultures that support the integration of work, family, and personal life. Work life initiatives should ideally be based on rationales that benefit companies and employees, including their families, well-being, and effectiveness. Large-scale organizational changes, such as firm restructuring, downsizing, and outsourcing, have been connected to physiological and mental health issues, presenteeism, and long-term sick leave in the past. . Formal and structural conditions that regulate work, such as employment contracts and work schedules, are examples of organizational work factors; legal and structural requirements that regulate how work is carried out, such as employment contracts and work schedules, are examples of organizational work factors. The organization attends to different change-related jobs and daily activities throughout a lifestyle change. One thing is constant as businesses deal with the always changing employment landscape: maintaining a connected and cared-for workforce is essential to developing a positive and supportive workplace culture. A company is only as good as the employees it has. In order to adapt and succeed in 2022 and beyond, organisations will need to go beyond their own financial

objectives and take into account the requirements of all of their employees. If you are what you consume, then the employees and policies of a company define it. This article presents an overview and definitions of lifestyle changes resulting from workplace culture. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; David, Ahmed, Ganeshkumar & Sankar, 2020; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pronk, Katz, Gallagher, Austin, Mullen, Lowry, & Kottke (2011) Optimal lifestyle activities are related to the emotional health of employees, the emotional health indicator like stress, depression can be studied to analyze the lifestyle activities of adults in their workplace. Elangovan, Eapen, Padmapriya, Nagaraj, Kannan, Ravi, & Merciline. (2021) The lockdown has shifted several lifestyle activities of implementing work from home, it is observed that employees from from obesity and suggested to consume fruits at regular intervals and shift in work hours. Mellor, & Webster (2013) Planning, interaction, monitoring, resourcing factors should be assessed continually by managers so as to compare the balance indirectly affecting the workplace culture. Payne, Cluff, Lang, Matson-Koffman, & Morgan-Lopez (2018) Leadership and co-worker support directly or indirectly aids in employee activity in the culture and health of employees. Environment and policy of organization are associated with lifestyle risk. So, the culture of health is dependent on employee activity. Hammer, Kossek, Anger, Bodner, Zimmerman (2009) Work family intervention is necessary to reduce the conflicts for an employee to maintain work life balance. so the conflict has an effect of decrement in health of employees.

Greenhaus, Powell. (2006) Experiences observed in one role in organization gives experiences to other role which helps in improving the quality of life and lifestyle. Model for enrichment process is examined. Gambles, Lewis, Rapoport (2006) the model identifies factors that pursuit high quality of with tensional nature, the interrelatedness and dynamic nature of work focuses on high quality of life in spite of changing environment. Eaton S (2003) the study observed among biotechnical employees is that flexibility given to the workers or employees has an optimistic outcome in results and increased productivity. The policies are adapted by organization's are changed according to the flexibility requirements of employees. it captures the organizational experience of working employees associated with the work life balance. Allen TD. (2001) the study aimed to identify employee perception towards work organization is family supportive. Job satisfaction, commitment, employee turnover, employee engagement are certain factors. the perception of overall environment determines the employee reactions to family friendly benefit policies

Conceptual Framework

Fig.1

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The information was gathered using a convenience sampling survey method, in which 30 people were given a standardized questionnaire and requested to fill it out. A comprehensive online vote chose participants in the study. The researcher used a Likert scale to gauge the employees' opinions. References from numerous journals, literature, books, and publications connected to the topic were consulted to support the research. Main research objectives are to study the employee resistance attitude towards organizational change. The questionnaire taking leadership, communication with peers/colleagues, and productivity factors as independent variables and lifestyle changes as a dependent variable.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Frequency of Demographic Variables

S. No	Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	18-24	24	80.0
		25-31	3	10.0
		32-40	2	6.7
		>40	1	3.3
2	Gender	Male	14	46.7
		Female	16	53.3
3	Occupation	Teacher/Professor	5	16.7
		It Professional	18	60.0
		Entrepreneur	4	13.3
		Service Employee	3	10.0
4	Work Experience	Fresher	19	63.3
		2-4 Years	8	26.7
		4-10 Years	1	3.3
		>10 Years	2	6.7

The frequency analysis is identified as maximum of 80% of respondents are belonging to the category of age group 18-24.the maximum of 46.7% of respondents belong to the category of gender are male. The maximum of 60% of respondents belong to the category of occupation are it professional. The maximum of 63% of respondents belong to the category of work experience are fresher's.

Table 2: Regression

Table 2.1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	.640 ^a	.409	.341	3.02012
A. Predictors: (Constant), Productivity, Leadership, Communication				

Table 2.2

Anova						
Model		Sum Of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	164.317	3	54.772	6.005	.003 ^b
	Residual	237.149	26	9.121		
	Total	401.467	29			
A. Dependent Variable: Lifestyle						
B. Predictors: (Constant), Productivity, Leadership, Communication						

Table 2.3

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.966	3.159		-.622	.539
	Leadership	.612	.291	.345	2.106	.045
	Communication	-.315	.237	-.235	-1.329	.195
	Productivity	.955	.285	.564	3.344	.003
a. Dependent Variable: Lifestyle						

The table shows the result of regression analysis.it is inferred that, significant value of productivity (0.003) and leadership (0.045) is lesser than 0.05. Hence, the independent variable leadership and productivity influences the dependent variable (lifestyle).

Table 3: Anova

S. No	Lifestyle	Age		Occupation		Work Experience	
		F	Sig	F	Sig	F	Sig
1	Leadership	1.600	0.182	.979	.486	3.375	.011
2	Communication	.692	.730	2.2125	.075	.385	.945
3	Productivity	.405	.905	1.356	.272	.879	.550

The table shows that the result of Anova, that has significant value of Accepting null hypothesis

CONCLUSION

While we believe that the shift in the workplace health promotion field toward a culture discussion will benefit employees, we are concerned that the overuse of the phrase "culture of health" will result in little substantive change in how employers and vendors approach creating a healthy workplace. If we keep in mind that "shared beliefs and behaviours" are at the core of culture, we can anticipate more effective employee health and well-being strategies. Our social connections and sway support health cultures, which makes it simpler for an employee base to sustain healthy behaviour changes and lower illness risks.

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